

Dynamic Synergies: Exploring Knowledge Exchange, Innovation, Creative Self-Efficacy, and Project Success in Public and Private Sector Organizations of Twin Cities, Pakistan

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Abstract

Through knowledge sharing, a firm is able to improve intelligence and decisions made since it allows for the sharing of information, skills, and expertise by employees. Since project success and innovation are essential for the organizational development and competitive advantage, respectively, creative self-efficacy, which is the confidence in one's ability to create solutions, impacts project success and innovation. The study aim to explore the relationships knowledge sharing, Project success, Innovation, and creative self-efficacy among the employee of public and private sector organizations of the twin city of Pakistan. This study adopted a cross-sectional research with sample size of 300 participants drawn from the both the public and the private sector organizations from twin cities of Islamabad and Rawalpindi. Information was gathered by structured questionnaires that were adopted from standardized indexes. Correlations and mediation test were also performed to establish the relationship between knowledge sharing and project success, innovation and creative self-efficacy. The study findings show that there are positive relationships between knowledge sharing and the level of project success, level of innovation, and level of creative self-efficacy in all the sectors and at all the locations which was researched. This paper establishes that knowledge sharing has a positive impact on project success and innovation, where creative self-efficacy moderates the effects. These studies assert that knowledge sharing is vital for developing innovation and improving the organizational performances in the GO and NGO sectors. Emphasizing knowledge sharing as an organizational value can pave the way to the envisioned organizational success implying further improvement in project performance. It is recommended that organizations should support activities that foster communication and cooperation in the framework of

knowledge sharing.

Keywords: knowledge sharing. Project success. Innovation. Creative self-efficacy. Employee. Public. Private sector. Organizations. Islamabad. Rawalpindi. Twin city. Pakistan

Introduction

As the field of organization and management, the role of understanding the complex relationships between KSH, project success, innovation, and creative self-efficacy of employees in public and private sector organizations belonging to the twin cities of Pakistan are most important study area. This study also seeks to establish how the interrelated factors, impact on organizational performance and competitiveness in a complex and dynamic economic environment.

Knowledge sharing has been identified as the process through which information, experience and understanding are passed from one employee to another in an organization (Supriatna, 2020; Tran et al., 2021; Ud Din Khan et al., 2023; Hadi & Sheikh, 2024). Regarding the subject of Twin cities of Pakistan and especially when the setting of environment contains both the public and private sectors having different functional models, the use and application of the concepts of knowledge management and more particularly of the concepts of knowledge sharing act as one of the significant factors that may either improve the teamwork and executive decisions or hinder in the organizations' progress.

Integral to this perspective is the idea of innovation that relates to the process of turning new ideas into realities and value-adding solutions that will respond to customers' needs and organization's objectives (Qureshi et al., 2019; Qureshi et al., 2020; Ibus et al., 2021; Bozdoğan & Aksoy, 2023; Laily et al., 2024). Before one goes further into what drives innovation, it is important to state that, creativity feeds from pooled knowledge where a range of inputs and an interacting different perspectives generate new approaches to the solution of problems and to products. It is therefore necessary to understand how knowledge sharing practices create and support innovation in both the public and private business sectors for continuity in improving and sustaining competitive advantage.

A component of creativity, self-confidence in one's ability to come up with unique solutions, appears as an antecedent to the implementation of knowledge and innovative results (Nguyen & Malik, 2020; Al Wali et al., 2022; Anwar & Humayun, 2023). Creativity self-efficacy thus means that those who possess high levels of it are more likely to engage in the knowledge sharing processes in a proactive manner and provide new ideas that push projects to their successful completion. This aspect of personal efficacy is not only effective in optimizing one's performance but also emerges as a key determinant of a team and organizational climate.

I found that the context of public sector organizations especially of twin cities in Pakistan enforces certain parameters which comprise of bureaucratic culture, rules, and regulation, and scarcity of resources that may influence the effectiveness of the knowledge sharing and innovation practices (Ahsan, 2019; Fayyaz et al., 2020; Zhang & Wang, 2022). On the other hand, private sector organizations are more motivated by economizing for profit and covering market demands, which chain shows more malleability of applying new knowledge and utilizing speedy shared knowledge for against competitors.

Vol. 2 No. 4 (November) (2024)

Study on these relationships has to follow a methodological approach where such variables like knowledge sharing behaviors, innovation outputs, levels of creative self-efficacy, as well as project success indicators have to be captured and measured quantitatively across different organizational settings. Comparing results obtained from studying public and private sector organizations allows the researchers to identify more clearly the factors enhancing or diminishing knowledge management and innovation in these sectors (Zhang & Bartol, 2010). The findings of this study are assumed to afford new information into the understanding of organizational behaviors and management practices within the two cities of Pakistan. Considering the case of a sector-based approach to knowledge sharing and creative self-efficacy, it is possible to identify effective practices that organizations can build upon to avert the challenges and thus, create cost efficient, effective and appropriate solutions to organizational needs and conflicts. Lastly, this study seeks to contribute to the advancement of research knowledge in the overall movement toward sustainable growth and development within various organizational contexts with a particular focus on management adaptability in organization's environments.

Research Question

- What is the relationship between knowledge sharing, Project success, Innovation, and creative self-efficacy among the employee of public and private sector organizations of the twin city of Pakistan?

Methodology

The present study used cross-sectional survey research design to analyze the nature and intensity of the knowledge sharing, project success, innovation, and creative self-efficacy of the employees working in the public and private sector organizations of the Twin cities of Pakistan. An available sample was used in the study since 300 employees completed the questionnaire. These sample sizes were calculated with the help of the G Power sample size calculator allowing to achieve enough statistical power for the analysis. The participants were evenly distributed across four categories: Those included Civil servants in Rawalpindi and Civic employees in Rawalpindi; employees working in the private sector in Rawalpindi; Civil servants in Islamabad; and employees in other private companies in Islamabad.

The study constructs were measured by four purposely developed questionnaires. Social capital was measured using another set of six items adopted from the work of Park & Lee (2014); and to improving the reliability, the Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.79. The variable innovation was operationalized by a ten-item questionnaire adopted from Wang & Wang (2012) where the reported reliability was a Cronbach's alpha of 0.86. The measure for creative self-efficacy was a 13-item scale adapted from Yang and Cheng (2009) that demonstrated good reliability with an alpha coefficient of 0.84. The evaluation of project success was done using a 14-item scale that was adopted from Aga, Noorderhaven and Vallejo, (2016); the scale showed high reliability by having a Cronbach's alpha of 0.83.

Some of the steps that were followed in data analysis procedures include the following. First, the descriptive statistics were used in order to calculate the

Vol. 2 No. 4 (November) (2024)

simple statistics regarding demographic data of the participants and assessment of study variables. Pearson product moment correlation analyses were then run on the Knowledge-sharing, innovation, creative self-efficacy and project success to establish their correlation. The data for this study were obtained from questionnaires that were filled by the respondents from October, 2023 to December 2023. To reduce common method variance, data on knowledge sharing, creative self-efficacy and innovation were gathered from the employees' supervisors, whereas the project success data were collected from the employees. On the issue of ethics there was compliance to the fact that the respondent's entry was voluntary and they were not identified individually in the study. Statistical data analysis was done using the statistical package for the social science (SPSS) version 28. This software allowed the usage of the analysis of variance to determine descriptive statistics to describe the demographic characteristics of the respondents and the major operational variables. To examine the research questions related to the level of knowledge sharing, innovation, creative self-efficacy and the level of project success, Pearson product – moment correlations were used in order to estimate both the strength and direction of these relationship in the researched organizational contexts. Issues of ethics that were considered in the study include participants' permission, anonymity and privacy of the participants and data, and utilization of the collected information solely for purposes of research. They include the following in order to promote and maintain the ethical practice when conducting Research and ensuring the participants' rights are not violated.

Results

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics (N = 300).

Sr.no	Variable	f	%
1	Age		
	18 – 27	45	15
	28 - 37	135	45
	38 – 47	75	25
	48 57	45	15
2	Gender		
	Male	153	51
	Female	147	49
4	Education Level		
	Intermediate	18	6
	Bachelor	143	48
	Master	75	25
	Above	62	21
7	Marital Status		
	Single	95	32
	Married	121	40
	Divorced	31	10
	Separated	38	13
	Widow/widower	15	5
8	Organization		
	Islamabad	75	25
	Public		

Rawalpindi	Private	75	25
	Public	75	25
	Private	75	25

Table 1 provides a snapshot of the demographic characteristics of the study participants (N = 300). It includes age distribution with varying proportions across different age groups, gender distribution showing an almost equal split, educational qualifications ranging from intermediate to advanced degrees, and marital status diversity. The organizational distribution indicates equal representation from public and private sectors in both Islamabad and Rawalpindi, each comprising 25% of the sample.

The comparison between the two sectors depicted in *Figure 1* reveals that private sector employee in Islamabad and Rawalpindi are indeed more knowledgeable in sharing their knowledge, and more successful with their projects, innovative and more creative self-efficacious than the public sector employees. It also manifests that as compared to the public sector organizations there is a higher degree of importance given to these characteristics specifically in the private sector organizations operating in the twin cities of Pakistan.

Table 2: Correlation of knowledge sharing, Project success, Innovation, and creative self-efficacy among the employee of public and private sector organizations of the twin city of Pakistan (N = 300).

Sr.no	Variables	N	M	S.D	KS	PS	Ino	CSE
1.	KS	300	26.67	1.26	-	.71**	.87**	.88**
2.	PS	300	66.71	1.21	-	-	.81**	.81**
3.	Ino	300	47.71	1.38	-	-	-	.87**
4.	CSE	300	61.71	1.91	-	-	-	-

Vol. 2 No. 4 (November) (2024)

Note: *N* = number of participants. *M* = mean. *S.D* = standard deviation. *KS* = knowledge sharing, *PS* = Project success, *Ino* = Innovation, *CSE* = creative self-efficacy

** = highly significant at .01

Table 2 The analysis made by using the responses, and presented, indicates that there is a strong positive correlation between the knowledge sharing and the project success, innovation, and creative self-efficacy. Likewise, project success has a direct relationship with innovation and creative self-efficacy, and Innovation in turn influenced by creative self-efficacy. These important relationships indicate that successful knowledge management improves project results, supports innovation, and promotes employees' self-confidence in their creativity.

Table 3: Separate Correlation of knowledge sharing, Project success, Innovation, and creative self-efficacy among the employee of public and private sector organizations of the twin city of Pakistan (N = 300).

Sr.no	Variables	N	M	S.D	KS	PS	Ino	CSE
Islamabad – Public								
1.	KS	75	26.76	1.95	-	.61*	.71**	.72**
2.	PS	75	64.71	1.25	-	-	.74**	.81**
3.	Ino	75	46.41	1.47	-	-	-	.76**
4	CSE	75	60.91	1.97	-	-	-	-
Islamabad – Private								
1.	KS	75	26.67	1.97	-	.83**	.69**	.71**
2.	PS	75	64.71	1.12	-	-	.74**	.81**
3.	Ino	75	46.41	1.43	-	-	-	.79**
4	CSE	75	60.91	1.96	-	-	-	-
Rawalpindi – Public								
1.	KS	75	26.67	1.93	-	.66**	.70**	.74**
2.	PS	75	64.71	1.27	-	-	.74**	.80**
3.	Ino	75	46.41	1.48	-	-	-	.74**
4	CSE	75	60.91	1.97	-	-	-	-
Rawalpindi – Private								
1.	KS	75	27.21	1.99	-	.81**	.73**	.73**
2.	PS	75	64.71	1.30	-	-	.76**	.84**
3.	Ino	75	46.41	1.44	-	-	-	.77**
4	CSE	75	60.91	1.96	-	-	-	-

Note: *N* = number of participants. *M* = mean. *S.D* = standard deviation. *KS* = knowledge sharing, *PS* = Project success, *Ino* = Innovation, *CSE* = creative self-efficacy

** = highly significant.

* = Significant.

Table 3 has provided the correlation for Islamabad and Rawalpindi separately for public and private sector employees. KS has significant positive relationships with PS, Ino, and CSE for all the groups. The correlations, though existent in both sectors, are usually higher in the private sector organizations. This means that in both cities and sectors, improved transformation of knowledge

encourages the delivery of better projects' results, high innovation, and increased creative self-efficacy among employees.

Discussion

The present study aimed at understanding the multiple relationships of the variables Knowledge sharing, Project success, Innovation and Creative self-efficacy in the employees of public and private organizations of twin cities in Pakistan. This is highlighted by the findings of the study which show that the aforementioned variables are linked; thus, availing the conditions for KMS sharing might lead to positive impacts on project outcomes, creative and innovative maturity levels, and self-efficacy among the employee participants. This indicate that; there is the interrelation between the culture and the practices as an influential factor that affects organizational performance in many organizations towards its innovation strategy.

It is concluded that knowledge sharing is positively correlated with the levels of project success; this is knowledge that is invaluable (Zia 2020; Alam et al., 2020; Xiao & Wang, 2023). This simply states that when information flows within the employees, concerning the skills and expertise, chances are likely to complete projects successfully. This is in accordance with Soomro et al (2023), that posited that risks on projects are reduced through knowledge sharing, the decision making capacity of a team is enhanced and guarantees that all the persons in a project team are alert. The implication for managers is clear: communication therefore should not be perceived as a luxury to have when a particular project is being conducted in an organization, rather it should be viewed as inevitable while implementing the goals of a given project in a workplace.

Here, the variable that mediates between knowledge sharing and the factors resulting from the implementation of the project indicates that the effects noted do not merely relate to the outcome of the concluded project but are vested in the sphere of organizational innovation and advancement. Bashir et al. (2023), concurrence with Don Abode's hypothesis that there is a direct correlation between knowledge sharing and innovation, that organizations which promote exchange of ideas and knowledge disseminating are also better placed to generate new end products, services, processes and concepts. The environment of dynamism in the advancement of technology in delivery of business solutions in which adaptability is said to be mother of success (Soomro et al., 2023; Saif et al., 2024). Fortunately, the matter is rather positive for both the public and private organizations and it reflects the enhancement of the innovative abilities by product of the proper sharing of knowledge (Sheeba & Christopher, 2023; Devi et al., 2024).

The self- efficacy to create also in the form of parachuted creativity using resources also gives positive correlations with knowledge sharing, successful completion of the project and innovations (Yasir et al., 2023; Rohma & Khoirunnisa, 2024). This entails that the employees with high self- assurance relating to creativity will be inclined to engage in knowledge sharing hence catalyze creation of innovations and therefore raise the probability of the accomplishment of projects (Chen et al., 2023; Sherpa & Bhattarai, 2024). This two-way feedback of this relationship reinforces that as the employees' engagement in knowledge sharing and innovation increases, there is a corresponding improvement in the creative self-efficacy and thus, creativity and

innovation are enhanced in a reciprocate cycle.

Further knowledge is gained from another division, where depending on the type of organizations, public sectors are separated from the private sectors. Other findings of the study include, the private sector employees scored higher than the public sector ones in all the aspects tapped more specifically in issues of knowledge sharing, project success, adoption of innovation and creative self-efficacy. This is due to the private sector which by general trends of operation is normally more variant and advised as compared to the civil service which concentrates more on stability (Oshineye, 2023; Hao et al., 2024). Apart from the said aspects, bureaucratic amongst other reasons may cause the public sector organizations to try out such practices which are commonly practiced in the private sector as a way of upping performance and innovation centers (Malake & Dharmasiri, 2023; Al Hawamdeh & AL-edenat, 2024).

Therefore, the limitations of this study, since convenience sampling may be used, the findings may not generalizable to other population and time points this is the strength of cross-sectional study where the temporal relations of two variables cannot be determined. Self-reported data are by their nature a measure of response bias, or reporting error. Similarly, generalizing the findings to other localities or countries may also limited when applying results to ascertain only Pakistan's twin cities. The following are the limitations of the present research and it is suggested for upcoming research that longitudinal, different sampling techniques and cross sectional designs should be used for the study across places. Actually, the essence of these findings for the organization policy and practice is great. It goes without saying that practices promoting the knowledge sharing of the firms should be embraced by organizations. That can be done for example through frequent meetings, proper tools and methods and formation of correct cross-functional teams. However, the practice of knowledge-sharing behavior could also be encouraged through positive identification and subsequent reward for behaviors that constitutes the company's organizational culture. For instance, in the performance assessments and bonuses, one gets to appreciate people's contribution in the distribution of knowledge and practice of innovation.

Moreover, leadership equally plays a significant role in establishing the right environment for the sharing of knowledge and creation of innovations. These behaviors should be exercised by the leaders, enhance communication processes within the departments, and also promote the knowledge sharing programs with adequate support. Moreover, any enhancement should be provided to the employees' professional activity to enhance the creative self-promotion of the firm's staff. Innovation could also be encouraged by ensuring that everyone accepts and implements ideas pertaining to them from the activities made, to promote the improvement of skills.

Conclusion

Knowledge sharing clearly indicates that this type of project management practice has a strong positive effect on project success especially with innovation acting as a moderator to the relationship. Creative self-efficacy also acts as a mediator to this effect enhancing the positive impact that knowledge sharing has on project results. In this way, knowledge sharing culture and increasing of employees' creative self-efficacy are organizational practices that can enhance innovation and project results. Such being the case, it is important that proper

measures be taken to encourage more open and clear communication as well as cooperative learning, and self confidence in other areas of creative performance among the organizations of the public and private sectors in Islamabad and Rawalpindi, Pakistan.

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Vol. 2 No. 4 (November) (2024)

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